

Fluctuations in weekly moth populations of 3 rice stem borers in Pakistan, 1972 and 1973.

Mo	Wk	Moths ^a (weekly total no.)					
		1972			1973		
		<i>Tryporyza innotata</i>	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>	<i>Tryporyza innotata</i>	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>
Mar	1	0	—	8	0	—	38
	2	0	0	36	0	—	49
	3	0	0	12	0	0	32
	4	75	0	16	0	0	16
Apr	1	162	12	1	75	0	7
	2	325	60	2	400	5	0
	3	1175 ^a	619	0	150	12	6
	4	995	710 ^b	2	108	8	4
May	1	300	655	2	441 ^b	350 ^b	0
	2	55	138	2	152	140	2
	3	30	72	0	50	50	3
	4	56	35	0	0	8	0
Jun	1	6	14	0	5	0	0
	2	10	5	0	12	15	3
	3	18	20	0	10	13	6
	4	5	3	0	0	5	0
Jul	1	0	1	0	2	5	0
	2	25	0	0	2	6	1
	3	20	5	0	8	5	2
	4	2	4	0	10	2	1
Aug	1	0	0	0		10	
	2	0	22	0	180	22	4
	3	16	12	3	307	63	1
	4	23	26	0	1640 ^b	71	3
Sep	1	58	28	3	1200	440	3
	2	386	1080 ^b	3	512	305	14
	3	420 ^b	770	3	125	378	
	4	120	415	6	47	1050 ^b	10
Oct	1	5	160	7	33	820	37
	2	1	80	25	5	450	41
	3	0	10	24	3	22	63
	4	0	0	18	0	0	52
Nov	1	0	0	7	0	0	22
	2	—	0	2	0	0	8
	3	—	—	0	0	0	0

^aVertical line indicates period when level of moth population was critical or alarming. ^bPeak level of moth population.

seems to be favored by mild, humid conditions.

Moth populations of the pink borer *Sesamia inferens* were highest in March and October; moths also emerged in

February and November in both 1972 and 1973. *S. inferens* requires comparatively lower temperature for emergence than *Tryporyza* spp. ■

Weed hosts of Diopsid (Diptera) rice stem borers in southern Nigeria

A. M. Alghali, postgraduate student (Entomology), Department of Agricultural Biology, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Weeds around paddy rice fields at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) were sampled for eggs, larvae, pupae, and adults of *Diopsis thoracica* West. In fields with rice at the heading stage, adult flies were observed on *Paspalum orbiculare* (Gramineae),

Cynodon dactylon (L) Pers. (Gramineae), and *Cyperus difformis* (Cyperaceae), but were more numerous on *C. difformis*. From 0 to 4 eggs/leaf, laid singly at the depression of the midrib, were found on *C. difformis*, while neither eggs, larvae, nor pupae were found on the others. In harvested fields, adults were seen on 1) sprouted seedlings from shattered rice grains left in the field from the previous crop, 2) ratoon rice crop from old stubbles, and 3) *C. difformis*. A larva was found inside the stem of *C. difformis*,

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- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

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- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number.

For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

and a pupa inside the leaf sheath from stubble of an unknown rice variety.

Evidence is insufficient to show that *P. orbiculare* and *C. dactylon* are alternate hosts; neither eggs, larvae, nor pupae were found on them. Possibly, the adult flies on the two weeds were only resting

between flights. However, *C. difformis*, found in almost all paddy rice areas around IITA, and ratoon rice plants, on which either eggs, larvae, pupae, or adults were found, could be host plants during the nonrice cropping period. ■

Soil and crop management

A convenient device for taking large undisturbed samples of paddy soil

E. T. Craswell, soil scientist, and E. G. Castillo, research aide, International Fertilizer Development Center-IRRI Cooperative Project. Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines

Soil scientists often need to take large, undisturbed cores of paddy soils for estimating bulk density or nutrient content on the basis of weight per unit area, or for conducting greenhouse

experiments with undisturbed soil.

A device for this purpose was recently developed at IRRI (see figure). The dimensions can be varied according to needs; we have also used a 20- x 20- x 60-cm version. The device consists of a box-shaped structure to take undisturbed soil samples and a sliding cover to facilitate removal of the bulk sample. Both parts are made of metal strong enough to gather and support the soil sample without distorting it.

To push the soil sampler into the soil, a block of wood is placed on top of it and struck with a sledge hammer. With the sampler at the required depth (as deep as 50 cm), the soil around it is dug away and the soil core is removed. Two men can collect a large sample (13 × 40 cm) in about 20 minutes.

Following is a typical example of data from Maahas clay (Aquic Tropudalf) collected at IRRI. The means are for 3 sampling depths with bulk densities computed for 9 cores, each 20 x 20 cm at the cross section. The high coefficients of variability are probably characteristic of the field site.

Depth (cm)	H ₂ O Content (% Oven dry basis)	CV (%)	Bulk density (g/cc)	CV (%)
0-15	84	9	0.66	10
15-30	56	12	0.91	6
30-50	57	12	0.84	15

We have taken 256 samples as part of a series of ¹⁵N balance experiments with no serious signs of wear on the soil samplers. ■

Diagram of a soil sampler designed to take large, undisturbed cores of paddy soils, IFDC - IRRI Cooperative Project.

CORRECTION

P.R. Hale. Two subterranean pests of upland rice in Papua New Guinea. IRRN 4:2 (April 1979). The correct address of P. R. Hale is Box 5144, Snowmass Village, Colorado 81615, USA.